

DONALD TRUMP'S NEIGHBORHOOD AGREEMENT

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Annotatsiya: Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari, Kanada va Meksika 2018 yil oxirida yangi savdo shartnomasini imzoladilar, u 1994 yilgi Shimoliy Amerika erkin savdo bitimini almashtiradi (eng yaxshi AQShga yo'naltirilgan qisqartma, AQSh-Meksika-Kanada kelishuvi yoki USMCA bilan mashhur) (NAFTA). Yangi pakt Tramp ma'muriyati boshqa mamlakatlarni AQShning proteksionistik iqtisodiy manfaatlari uchun qulayroq shartlarni qabul qilishga majburlash maqsadida bir tomonlama tariflar joriy qilganidan keyingi birinchi yirik savdo kelishuvidir. Garchi hali tasdiqlanmagan bo'lsa-da, shartnoma asosan Qo'shma Shtatlar kelajakdagi xalqaro savdo muzokaralariga qanday yondashishi uchun namuna sifatida ko'riladi.

Kalit so'zlar. NAFTA, USMCA, Trump, avtomobil ishlab chiqarish, farmatsevtika, nizolarni hal qilish, yuk tashish, patentlar va savdo belgilari, kunlik mahsulotlar bozori.

Аннотация: Соединенные Штаты, Канада и Мексика подписали новый торговый договор в конце 2018 года, который заменит Североамериканское соглашение о свободной торговле 1994 года (наиболее известное по его аббревиатуре, ориентированной на США, Соглашение между США, Мексикой и Канадой или USMCA) (НАФТА). Новый пакт является первым крупным торговым соглашением, подписанным после одностороннего введения администрацией Трампа тарифов в попытке заставить другие страны принять условия, более благоприятные для протекционистских экономических интересов США. Несмотря на то, что он еще не утвержден, пакт в значительной степени рассматривается как модель того, как Соединенные Штаты будут подходить к будущим международным торговым переговорам.

Ключевые слова. NAFTA, USMCA, Трамп, автопроизводство, фармацевтика, разрешение споров, грузоперевозки, патенты и товарные знаки, молочный рынок.

Abstract: The United States, Canada, and Mexico signed another swap agreement in late 2018 to replace the 1994 North American Free Trade Agreement (most commonly known by its US acronym, US-Mexico-Canada Agreement, or USMCA). The new settlement is a first major swap deal approved as a result of the Trump Administration's unilateral use of fees in an attempt to force different countries to accept terms more favorable to US protectionist financial interests. Despite the fact that it has yet to be approved, the pact is largely seen as a model for how the United States would approach future international trade talks.

Keywords. *NAFTA, USMCA, Trump, auto manufacturing, pharmaceuticals, dispute resolution, trucking, patent and trademark, diary market.*

As we know, Donald Trump became a president who wanted to lower the country's trade deficit with some nations. It is clear that Donald Trump was a successful entrepreneur and during his presidency, the administration mostly leaned on economic issues such as trade deficit problems with foreign actors. Therefore, firstly Trump decided to refresh the trade agreement of NAFTA, which deal with two neighbors (Canada and Mexico). During Trump's presidency, the agreement of NAFTA has been transformed into a new deal to USMCA. The president pointed out that the agreement of NAFTA was not working properly and it has to be refreshed. During an interview with the Associated Press on April 24, 2017, Trump said, "I am very upset with NAFTA. I think NAFTA has been a catastrophic trade deal for the United States, a trading agreement for the United States. It hurts us with Canada, and it hurts us with Mexico. Most people do not even think of NAFTA in terms of Canada. You saw what happened yesterday in my statements because if you look at the dairy farmers in Wisconsin and upstate New York, they are getting killed by NAFTA." When asked if he would renegotiate NAFTA, Trump said, "I am going to either renegotiate it or I am going to terminate it. ... If they don't treat fairly, I am terminating NAFTA." When asked what the timeline was for terminating NAFTA, Trump said, "It's a six-month termination clause, I have the right to do it, and it's a six-month clause."⁴

Renegotiation of NAFTA. On August 16, 2017, renegotiations for the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) began. President Donald Trump has selected Robert Lighthizer to be the US Trade Representative. Both Canada and Mexico sought to replace the NAFTA pact, which was out of date. It did not, for example, address internet commerce or mandate that environmental and labor safeguards included in side agreements be considered.⁵

On March 5, 2018, the seventh round of renegotiations was held. It was a long and winding road. On May 31, 2018, Trump introduced a 25 percent tax on steel in Canada, Mexico, and the European Union. In response, Canada demanded a \$12.6 billion levy on US goods.⁶

The Implementation of USMCA. On September 30, 2018, the last conversations were completed, in line with the deadline set by President Trump. He needed to inform Congress 90 days in advance before he could mark the settlement. He planned for this

⁴ **Associated Press.** *An Interview between Donald Trump and Journalist.*

<https://apnews.com/c810d7de280a47e88848b0ac74690c83>

⁵ **Congressional Research Service.** *"The North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA).* May 24, 2017

<https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/R/R42965>

⁶ **Utah Department of Agriculture and Food.** *"NASDA Analysis of U.S. Tariffs and Foreign Retaliatory Tariffs*

<https://aq.utah.gov/documents/NASDAAnalysisofU.S.TariffsandForeignRetaliatoryTariffs%206-25-18.pdf>

to happen before the next Mexican president, Andrés Manuel López Obrador, took office on December 1, 2018.

It was in this spirit that forwarded to each country's legislators for ratification. In the event that Congress does not support the USMCA whenever it is flagged, Trump could take steps to terminate NAFTA.⁷

On January 29, 2020, Donald Trump signed the USMCA agreement, which has bipartisan support. Before the USMCA could take effect, each of the three nations had to accept it. Mexico was the first country to sign the pact in June 2019. Canada authorized it on March 13, 2020.

The United States-Mexico-Canada Pact (USMCA) is the most extensive and high-stakes economic agreement ever signed. It thoroughly modernizes, rebalances, and renews NAFTA to meet the demands of the twenty-first century economy, ensuring that it benefits American workers, ranchers, farmers, and entrepreneurs, particularly small and medium-sized businesses. This was necessary to foster financial development, a more even-handed and balanced trade, and to keep North America as the world's most competitive area.

In addition, the USMCA revision introduced several new changes to the previous understanding of NAFTA in a particular region, and they related to pharmacy, intellectual property, automobile manufacturing, truck standards, the dairy market, technological sector and dispute resolutions.

Canadian dairy market. Farmers from the United States must have access to Canada's dairy market. For things of class 6 and 7, it will leave its confusing evaluation mechanism. Milk protein concentration, skim milk powder, and newborn formula are all examples of this. It also allows for increased marketing of certain American cheeses in Canada.⁸

Dispute Settlement. At this time, Chapter 19 of NAFTA may no longer be used by businesses to settle disputes with governments. The oil companies in the United States represent one intriguing special case. They fear that Mexico can actually nationalize its oil industry.⁹

The NAFTA Chapter 11 Dispute Resolution Panels are still in place. These arbitration tribunals decide whether a NAFTA country acted unjustly against a partner's abroad interests. The panels ensure that American firms uphold the rights guaranteed by the US Constitution.¹⁰

⁷ **The White House.** "Remarks by President Trump in Press Gaggle Aboard Air Force One.

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefings-statements/remarks-president-trump-press-gaggle-aboard-air-force-one-2/>

⁸ **Office of the United States Trade Representative.** "United States-Mexico-Canada Trade Face Sheet Agriculture: Market Access and Dairy Outcomes of the USMC Agreement. <https://ustr.gov/trade-agreements/free-trade-agreements/united-states-mexico-canada-agreement/fact-sheets/market-access-and-dairy-outcomes>

⁹ **Journal of International Arbitration.** "The New NAFTA: Scaled-Back Arbitration in the USMCA. <https://www.alston.com/-/media/files/insights/publications/2019/12/the-new-nafta.pdf>

¹⁰ **Cato Institute.** "Knowing Your NAFTA Dispute Chapters: 11 vs. 19 vs. 20. <https://www.cato.org/blog/knowing-nafta-dispute-chapters-11-vs-19-vs-20>

Trucking. The USMCA has language that offers American drivers huge benefits in the country, which raised some questions from experts. Here is what this expression explains:

- A Mexican carrier cannot carry shipments leaving the US and ending in the US.
- The Department of Transportation can decide if a Mexican carrier has allowed flights within the United States. Carriers who have been cleared by the USMCA will be transferred under the new rules.

There are no such restrictions for Canadian drivers. Whatever the case, American riders will see any decline in the worldwide competition as a perfect win. Patents and trademarks

Fourth, the new arrangement ensures a higher level of security for licenses and trademarks. A large number of intellectual property insurances negotiated under the Trans-Pacific Partnership have been accepted, despite Trump's opposition to the agreement.¹¹

Pharmaceuticals

The USMCA intellectual property rules for pharmaceuticals have been significantly revised and represent a significant step forward for public health, not only for the three participating countries, but also for future discussions with the US.

The USMCA originally featured a clause that gave biologics ten years of market exclusivity, which was a problematic issue given rising medication costs. The provision in the USMCA that allowed secondary patenting of new uses for a known product, new uses for a known product, or new uses for a known product has been abolished totally.

Auto manufacturing sector. NAFTA's auto regulations were outdated, allowing countries outside of North America to "ride for free" and stifle U.S. auto production and businesses. The USMCA proposes improved auto and auto parts launch rules to help protect and relocate auto and parts manufacturing, as well as more incentives for the U.S. auto industry.

Such changes should create more jobs for auto workers in the United States. However, this may reduce the number of positions in the US associated with the creation of cars available for purchase in China. Vehicles will be prohibitively expensive for the Chinese market due to higher US operating costs. Cars bought in the US will also cost more. This also means that several small cars will be taken off the market in North America.¹²

Conclusion. The U.S.M.C.A. makes a significant shift by repealing a unique arbitration system that permitted businesses to challenge governments for unfair

¹¹ Office of the United States Trade Representative. "United States-Mexico-Canada Trade Face Sheet Modernizing NAFTA into a 21st Century Trade Agreement. <https://ustr.gov/trade-agreements/free-trade-agreements/united-states-mexico-canada-agreement/fact-sheets/modernizing>

¹² Center for Automotive Research. "U.S. Consumer & Economic Impacts of U.S. Automotive Trade Policies. <https://www.cargroup.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/US-Consumer-Economic-Impacts-of-US-Automotive-Trade-Policies-.pdf>

treatment. Both the Trump administration and Democrats have opposed the clause, claiming that it encourages outsourcing and gives companies too much authority to challenge environmental and consumer protections.

This structure is currently not suitable for debates between the United States and Canada, and it is simply suitable for issues between Mexico and the United States, including a limited number of businesses such as petrochemicals, media, funds, and power generation.

Various strategies for dealing with state issues have largely been retained. After all, the Trump administration backed its push to cancel a proposed Chapter 19 deal that allows the three countries to question each other's responsibilities and various non-partisan assembly demonstrations. The administration also agreed to revoke the agreement, which would have allowed any country to prevent arguments being made against it if it were so necessary due to Democrats' fears.

The USMCA, on the other hand, has a more polarizing Trump administration amendment: a sunset clause that requires the three nations to determine whether to continue in the pact after six years. The agreement will expire 16 years after any country decides not to continue with it.

Instead of improving public health protection, the USMCA imposes new, expanded, and enforceable requirements on public regulators, giving corporate (investor) interests more authority (voice) throughout the creation of new rules. It is not a health-improving model that countries should follow in future trade deals.

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